

Sustainable soil treatment: Investigating the efficacy of carrageenan biopolymer on the geotechnical properties of soil

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Biopolymer treated soil
Carrageenan
Unconfined compressive strength
Static triaxial test
SEM
FTIR

ABSTRACT

The employment of novel biopolymers offers geotechnical engineers a diverse range of materials to choose from, depending on the specific requirements of different projects. Regarding the promotion of environmentally friendly materials in the construction industry, this study introduces carrageenan as a novel biopolymer for soil improvement. The research also includes a comparative study of carrageenan's performance with xanthan which is the most commonly used biopolymer in geotechnical engineering. Unconfined compressive tests (UCS) were conducted to evaluate the performance of biopolymer-treated soil samples over a variety of effective parameters including biopolymer content, moisture content, curing time, soil particle size, and durability under wet-dry cycles. In order to explore the soil size effect, kaolinite silt and sand were combined in various proportions and treated with different biopolymer ratios to enhance strength development. The optimal mix of each biopolymer-treated soil was then exposed to five cycles of wetting and drying. Carrageenan improved the compressive strength of untreated soils in all cases, for example 3.4 times for 0.5% (w_b/w_s) of biopolymer. In higher proportions of kaolinite, carrageenan performed considerably better than xanthan gum in terms of compressive and shear strength. In addition, with an emphasis on confining pressures, static triaxial experiments were conducted to examine the effectiveness of carrageenan, by which it was shown that carrageenan outperforms xanthan in terms of shear strength especially in the fine-grained soil. The mechanism and chemical interaction behind the significant performance of carrageenan in binding soil grains, increasing mechanical strength and improving durability of the soil was also studied through FTIR analysis and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images. It can be concluded that carrageenan can be considered as a sustainable alternative to conventional materials such as cement and lime.

1. Introduction

Walking towards a greener environment and having zero environmental impact from engineering practices, it highlights the importance of developing the current available methods and materials and looking for new opportunities. While conventional materials offer advantages from the mechanical properties overview, they leave detrimental and some irreversible impacts on the environment [1–6]. Almost 5% of global CO₂ emissions are contributed to the cement industry [7,8], leading to global warming and severe biodiversity damage [9,10]. In this way, biological techniques have recently been developed to minimize the environmental impacts, e.g., microbial-induced calcite precipitation (MICP) [11–15], enzyme-induced calcite precipitation (EICP)

[16–18], biogas generation, and biopolymers [15,19–24]. Calcite-induced precipitation methods precipitate calcite through the hydrolysis of urea.

Biopolymers are natural polymers produced by living organisms classified into three divisions: polynucleotides, polypeptides, and polysaccharides [25]. Biopolymers are sustainable, low-carbon, and renewable resources as nature are their production source. Polysaccharides have been known for their potential and effectiveness in improving soil properties [26,27]; biopolymers such as xanthan, gellan, guar gum, alginate, and agar remarkably improve the mechanical properties of the soil [28–32]. Animal-based biopolymers have also effectively increased the soil strength [33–36]. Researchers have applied biopolymers in various geotechnical applications, such as surface erosion prevention,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2023.134627>

Received 19 July 2023; Received in revised form 12 December 2023; Accepted 13 December 2023

Available online 21 December 2023

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slope stability, soil strengthening, hydraulic barriers, and subgrade improvement [37–44].

In development a new material, highlighting the key factors influencing the behavior of BPTS is critical. In this context, biopolymer content, biopolymer concentration, moisture content, temperature, soil type, and dehydration time are the most important factors [19,45]. Generally, the strength is increased by higher biopolymer content (to the mass of soil) up to an optimum level that a higher biopolymer amount is no longer effective [28,46–48]. Less moisture content increases the BPTS strength, especially for water-soluble biopolymers [49]. For many biopolymers, thermal conditions in the preparation stage determine the uniformity of the BPTS mixture. For thermogelatin biopolymers, the impact of temperature is pivotal as biopolymer and soil should be mixed in specific temperature ranges [32,50]. Dehydration time is inversely dependent on the moisture content; the longer the dehydration time, the lower the moisture content [10,36,51].

Xanthan gum is the most common biopolymer utilized in geotechnical applications because of its unique functional properties. As a benchmark, it is useful to fundamentally investigate how xanthan has been developed through various research so that the same approach can be taken when introducing a new material. High stability at a wide range of temperatures, ionic salt compatibility, pH stability, and pseudoplasticity are excellent characteristics of xanthan [52,53]. As a soil strengthener, xanthan is able to provide bonds by coating and building bridges between soil grains [54,55]. The presence of xanthan gum in the soil increases the compressive and shear strength [56,57], erosion resistance [58], soil consistency [59], and also reduces the hydraulic conductivity due to the clogging effect [60]. The durability and strength of two dispersive soils were remarkably improved by adding 1% xanthan gum after 360 days of curing and 12 wet-dry cycles [61]. In a triaxial investigation, it was concluded that when the biopolymer film matrix was fully developed, the shear resistance of sand was significantly improved, and there was a noticeable improvement in cohesion and the friction angle [62].

Carrageenan is a marine biopolymer that comprises natural linear sulfated polysaccharides [63]. Few studies have studied the potential of utilizing carrageenan as a binder in construction applications. The use of carrageenan in earthen construction has been reported, resulting in modification of water durability and mechanical properties [64]. Carrageenan was applied to prevent soil loss induced by water flow and wind forces. A noticeable reduction was observed after adding a small amount of biopolymer, showing its capacity to form a resistant crust against different driving forces [37,49].

Utilization of new biopolymers for soil improvement represents a notable advancement in sustainable construction practices. The continuous discovery of novel biopolymers gives engineers the opportunity of having a wide range of options which allows them for more tailored solutions to meet specific project requirements. Plus, this diversity of options not only promotes creativity but also enables each location to pick their best and most cost-effective material based on their need. Furthermore, availability of different options removes the difficulty of importing and transportation of materials for a project.

In the field of soil treatment applications, the potential of carrageenan biopolymer has been relatively unexplored. Recognizing this gap, an effort has been made to comprehensively assess the impact of carrageenan on both mechanical and durability properties of the treated soil. This evaluation involved a series of geotechnical and microstructural tests, including the determination of unconfined compressive strength (UCS), consolidated drained (CD) triaxial tests, examination of scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images, and FTIR analysis. Initially, UCS tests were performed to identify the optimal biopolymer content and curing time. Subsequently, various combinations of kaolinite and sand were employed to explore the influence of soil type. The most suitable soil mixture was then employed to investigate the durability of the treated soil after undergoing five wet-dry cycles. Furthermore, triaxial tests were conducted to examine the impact of

carrageenan treatment on the shear strength of different soil types under varying confining pressures. SEM images, FTIR analysis, and the application of a schematic soil-biopolymer interaction model were employed to enhance the understanding of the underlying mechanisms responsible for strengthening. Throughout the study, xanthan was utilized as a control agent to assess the performance of carrageenan. Upon completion of this study, our anticipation is to introduce carrageenan as a novel alternative to traditional materials and this paper is considered as a comprehensive source for researchers and engineers to reach a valuable insight into carrageenan-treated soil behavior.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Kaolinite

Kaolinite silt was acquired from the Kaolin Malaysia company, which specializes in mining products. The kaolinite was extracted from depths between 4.0 to 6.0 m beneath the ground. The XRD analysis indicates that aluminum silicate is the main chemical constituent of the kaolinite silt (Table 1). The kaolinite silt also consists of other minor components in lower extents, such as K_2O and Fe_2O_3 . Table 2 provides the geotechnical specifications of the used kaolinite; as seen, the soil contains 78% of silt, 21.12% of clay, and 0.88% of sand, performing the particle size distribution and hydrometer analyses [65,66]. Based on the Unified Soil Classification System (USCS), the soil is classified as high-plasticity kaolinite silt (MH) with the Skempton activity value of 0.77%.

2.2. Sand

The construction site where the sand was collected was in Gold Coast, Australia. In accordance with USCS, the sand is classified as poorly-graded sand (SP). Fig. 1 shows the gradation analysis of both kaolinite silt and sand used in this study. As seen, the gradation coefficient (C_u) and the uniformity coefficient (C_u) are 0.91 and 2.77, respectively. The structural composition of the soil is between the minimum void ratio of 0.61 and the maximum void ratio of 0.76. Table 3 presents the chemical constituents of the sand obtained by the XRD analysis. Also, Table 4 shows the sand geotechnical properties.

2.3. Xanthan

Xanthan ($C_{35}H_{49}O_{29}$) is a polysaccharide biopolymer formed through the fermentation of sugar by a bacteria called *Xanthomonas campestris* [67]. Xanthan is typically utilized in the food industry as a non-toxic thickening agent to stabilize food ingredients [68]. Xanthan has an ionic surface characteristic that facilitates the interaction with cationic materials [68]. A stable viscous gel (even at low concentrations) was formed after mixing properly with water. Due to its consistent rheology, xanthan has been utilized as a drilling mud stabilizer in the oil industry. It has also been used as a binder in concrete for viscosity enhancement and washout prevention [69]. Xanthan gum used for this study was purchased from Glenthams Life Sciences company with CAS No. 11138–66–2. It was a white to off-white or faint beige powder with no odor and taste.

Table 1
XRD analysis of MH silt.

Component	Percentage (%)
SiO_2	48.97
Al_2O_3	35.19
K_2O	2.51
Fe_2O_3	0.88
MgO	0.35
TiO_2	0.23

Table 2
Geotechnical properties of the kaolinite silt.

Soil Type	Sand fraction (%)	Silt fraction (%)	Clay fraction (%)	L _L (%)	P _L (%)	P _I (%)	USCS	Activity = P _I /Clay content (%)
Kaolinite	0.88	78.00	21.12	62	46	16	MH	0.77

Fig. 1. Particle size distribution of kaolinite silt and sand.

Table 3
XRD analysis of sand.

Component	Percentage (%)
Quartz	76.5
Calcite	3.4
Dolomite	0.1
Siderite	0.7
Siderite (Mg/CA)	2.2
Andradite	1.0
Plagioclase (An0–15)	7.7
K-Feldspar	3.0
Kaolinite	0.9
Chlorite	1.4
Illite	3.2

Table 4
Geotechnical properties of the used sand.

Soil type	D ₅₀ (mm)	C _u	C _c	G _s	Shape	UCSC	e _{min}	e _{max}
Sand	0.49	2.77	0.91	2.63	Round	SP	0.61	0.76

2.4. Carrageenan

Red edible seaweeds are used to produce the carrageenan biopolymer, known as a linear polysaccharide. Carrageenan is a soluble biopolymer with the chemical formula of C₂₄H₃₆O₂₅S₂, and in the food sector, it is frequently employed as a thickening and gelling agent [70]. There are three commercially available types of carrageenan including kappa (κ), lambda (λ), and iota (ι). The main differences that affect the properties of these three types are in the position and number of the ester sulfate groups on the repeating galactose units; the greater extents of ester sulfate, the lower the gel strength and solubility temperature [71]. Carrageenan used for this study was Kappa-Carrageenan produced by the Tokyo Chemical industry (TCI) with CAS No. 11114–20–8, an odorless solid powder with a slightly pale-yellow color.

2.5. Sample preparation

The wet mixing method, chosen for both xanthan and carrageenan,

aimed at maximizing productivity [19,64,68]. In this process, a specified quantity of distilled water was heated to 70 °C to enhance solubility. The biopolymer was gradually introduced into the hot water and manually mixed for five to ten minutes until a homogeneous solution was attained. Subsequently, the oven-dried soil (105 °C for 24 h) was blended with the solution for an additional ten minutes to ensure a uniform soil-biopolymer mixture. Following this, a small sample was extracted for moisture content measurement, while the remainder was stored in a sealed bag for 24 h to ensure even moisture distribution throughout the mixture.

For maintaining consistency in sample preparation, a specially designed mold was fabricated in compliance with ASTM D4609 and ASTM D2850 [72,73]. The primary component of the mold was a cylindrical stainless-steel tube with two wings welded to the sides. Additional components included a stainless-steel square plate, plug, short and long hammers. The cylinder dimensions were set at 50 mm in diameter and 200 mm in height. During sample fabrication, lubrication was applied to the surfaces of the plug, short hammer, and the inner side of the tube. The prepared mixture was then inserted into the mold, and the square plate was employed to adjust the mold position. Compaction was achieved in one layer using a hydraulic jack, with the compaction load applied until surpassing 90% of the maximum density determined by the compaction test. The compacted specimens were extruded post-compaction and subjected to curing in a controlled environment at 50–60% relative humidity and 23 °C. Samples for UCS and triaxial testing were cylindrical with dimensions of 50 mm in diameter and 100 mm in height.

2.6. Experimental program

The selection of specific tests in this study, including the compaction test, UCS test, triaxial test, FTIR analysis, and SEM imaging, was performed by their relevance to evaluating the impact of biopolymers on soil engineering properties. The compaction test provided essential outcome on maximum dry densities and optimum moisture contents, crucial for precise sample preparation. The UCS and triaxial tests were employed to assess the mechanical characteristics of the treated soil. Additionally, FTIR analysis and SEM imaging were utilized to reach microstructural insights into the interaction between biopolymers and

soil components. The reason for choosing each test was based on their ability to comprehensively capture the changes induced by biopolymers. The experimental design, including the variation of parameters such as biopolymer content, curing time, soil type effect, and durability under wet-dry cycles, aimed to explore a range of conditions to provide a comprehensive understanding of the biopolymer-soil interaction. The detailed experimental program for the study can be found in Table 5.

To recognize different specimens, a labeling scheme is applied that includes three parts, the first part is for the kaolinite-sand combination consisting of four parts: K as kaolinite, a number from 0 to 4, S as sand, and a number from 0 to 4. For instance, K3S1 indicates a kaolinite-sand mixture with 3 parts of kaolinite and 1 part of sand. The second part shows the biopolymers and the corresponded contents (in a mass ratio to the soil), Xa for Xanthan gum and CA for Carrageenan. The third is for showing the curing days of the specimens. For example, K2S2-Xa0.5-14 referred to soil (50% of kaolinite and 50% of sand) stabilized by 0.5% xanthan gum cured for 14 days. In the case of wet-dry cycles, the last part is replaced with the number of cycles (from 1 to 5) as the curing time for all durability samples was 14 days.

2.7. Kaolinite-sand combination

To investigate the influence of soil type on the unconfined compressive strength of biopolymer-treated soil, different sand-kaolinite mixtures were obtained by mixing dry sand and kaolinite at the mass ratios (K3S1; means three parts of kaolinite and 1 part of sand) listed in Table 6. The compaction tests were performed in accordance with ASTM D698-12 to prepare the samples according to the optimum moisture content (OMC) and maximum dry density (MDD) [74]. 12.86% was obtained as OMC for K1S3 which was inadequate to prepare a homogeneous biopolymer solution, so 15% of water content was considered in this regard [75].

2.7.1. Unconfined compressive strength test

The unconfined compressive strength was determined using Universal Testing Machine in accordance with ASTM D2166 [72]. The UCS tests were used to determine optimum values and evaluate the effect of various parameters on the biopolymer-treated soil behavior, including biopolymer content, dehydration time, soil type effect, and durability under wet-dry cycles. The axial strain rate was controlled at 1%/min (1 mm/min) and continued up to 7% of the total strain, where the stress-strain behavior was automatically tracked and recorded by the machine. Three specimens were repeated for each condition and the average was reported as the unconfined compression strength.

2.7.2. Triaxial test

Triaxial samples were prepared in the same condition as for UCS test and cured in a designated room where the temperature was carefully regulated to be 23 °C and the relative humidity ranged from 50 to 60%. Afterwards, the samples were subjected to consolidated drained (CD)

Table 5 Experimental program of the current study on CA and XA.

Test type	Biopolymer content (%)	Curing time (days)	Soil type	No. of wet-dry cycles
UCS	0, 0.25, 0.5, 1, 1.5	14	K4S0, K1S3	-
	0, 0.5	0, 1, 3, 7, 14, 28	K4S0, K1S3	-
	0, 0.5	14	K4S0, K3S1, K2S2, K1S3, K0S4	-
Triaxial	0, 0.5	14	K1S3	0, 1, 2, 3, 5
	0, 0.5	14	K4S0, K1S3	-
SEM	0.5	14	K4S0, K1S3, K0S4	-
FTIR	0.5	14	K1S3	-

Table 6 Sand-kaolinite mixtures.

Label	Soil (%)			Optimum moisture content (%)	Maximum dry density (gr/cm ³)
	Sand	Silt	Clay		
K4S0	0	80	20	35.13	1.37
K3S1	25	60	15	29.88	1.57
K2S2	50	40	10	20.25	1.75
K1S3	75	20	5	12.86	2.04
K0S4	100	0	0	16.75	1.83

triaxial testing according to ASTM D7181 [76].

The tests were performed with a laboratory triaxial testing machine shown in.

Fig. 2. To avoid contact with the pressurized chamber fluid, the test samples were placed on the bottom plate with a rubber membrane, and porous stones were positioned above and below them. The experimental system was connected to a computer-controlled triaxial device. Additionally, the top of the chamber contained a linear variable differential transformer that was external for measuring the axial strain. The strain rate was 0.1 mm/min and the confinement pressures were 50 kPa, 100 kPa, and 200 kPa.

2.7.3. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images

SEM images were taken to observe the structure and micro-scale interaction of biopolymer and soil. Biopolymer gel, untreated soil (sand, kaolinite, K1S3), and biopolymer-treated soils were used for SEM characterization. The samples were kept in the oven at 35 °C for 24 h to ensure dryness. Then, carbon conductive tabs were used to fasten them to a SEM mount. Using carbon paint to provide adequate electric grounding, samples were then covered with conductive tape. The specimen was observed using a Zeiss Sigma VP Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (Oberkochen, Germany).

2.7.4. Attenuated total reflectance fourier transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectroscopy

ATR-FTIR spectroscopy is a type of spectroscopy that is commonly used to analyze the chemical composition of substances. To determine the functional groups present in both untreated and treated soils, ATR-FTIR analysis was carried out using a Bruker Tensor27-spectrometer within a range of 400 to 4000 cm⁻¹. To prepare the soil samples for analysis, a technique called the potassium bromide (KBr) disc technique was used at a ratio of 100:1 (KBr to soil).

3. Results

3.1. Unconfined compression strength (UCS) test

3.1.1. Biopolymer content

The compressive strength values for untreated and treated soils with various amounts of carrageenan and xanthan (0, 0.25, 0.5, 1, 1.5% by weight to dry soil) are shown in Fig. 3. The treated samples were kept in a controlled room with a temperature of 23 °C and humidity of 50–60% for 14 days. Based on the compaction test results, the initial moisture contents for K4S0 and K1S3 specimens were considered as 35% and 15%, respectively.

In general, carrageenan outperforms xanthan in various aspects, exhibiting high effectiveness in fine-grained soils. With its water-attracting properties and enhanced workability, carrageenan demonstrates superior strength enhancement. It excels in treating fine-grained soils, while xanthan shines in enhancing the strength of fine-grained soils with some coarse particles, highlighting their distinct advantages in soil improvement for enhanced mechanical properties. As seen in Fig. 3, the samples gain higher strength and stiffness by adding carrageenan up to 0.5% and then a decrease is observed.

For the treated-K4S0, the average strength increment, at its highest

Fig. 2. Triaxial testing system and a sample in the cell.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. UCS test results, (a) Compressive strength of K4S0-treated soil, (b) Compressive strength of K1S3-treated soil.

level, was 340%, and 175% at its lowest level. In the case of K1S3-treated soil, the highest and lowest enhancements were, respectively, 349% and 281%. The reduction in the compressive strength after 0.5% can be related to the formation of more biopolymer gel than the required amount to entangle with soil particles. The extra gel treats as a lubricant which causes the unconstrained movements of grains and results in less interaction and hence strength reduction.

As shown in Fig. 3, even though the xanthan treatment increases both compressive strength and elasticity modulus in all cases, the increment rates of strength in K1S3 samples are significantly higher than K4S0 samples. For instance, a growth value of 428% was obtained for xanthan-treated K1S3 (0.5%) in comparison to 42% of increment for the similar K4S0 sample. This difference in the improvement values is due to the difficulty of biopolymer solution distribution across the kaolinite soil

because the used kaolinite was a light soil with a very hydrophilic hydroxyl surface [77]. Furthermore, the thick shape of the prepared xanthan solution, due to its high water absorption capacity [78], exacerbated the circumstances of reaching a uniform soil-biopolymer mixture.

3.1.2. Curing time

The curing time effect on the UCS of the fine-grained soil (K4S0) and the clayey-sandy soil (K1S3) treated with carrageenan and xanthan was investigated. The specimens, treated with 0.5% biopolymers (by weight of dry soil), were cured for different durations (0, 1, 3, 7, 14, and 28 days) in a controlled room at 23 °C and 60% humidity. Fig. 4 illustrates the variations in UCS and moisture content over time.

From the graphs in Fig. 4, it is evident that carrageenan exhibited a higher increase in the compressive strength of the fine-grained soil

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Unconfined compressive strength and moisture content of biopolymer-treated soil over time. a) Treated K4S0, b) Treated K1S3.

(K4S0) compared to xanthan over time. Initially, the treated specimens showed similar strength values to the untreated soil (270 ± 50 kPa), indicating the initial ineffectiveness of the biopolymer gel. However, an increasing trend in strength was observed with curing time, with the majority of the strength gain occurring within the first 7 days of curing. After 14 days, the strength of the treated soil samples reached its maximum and remained relatively constant until day 28, establishing 14 days as the optimum curing time for further analysis.

The observed increase in compressive strength over time is directly associated with the reduction in moisture content. Initially, moisture is essential for the dissolution of the biopolymer in the solvent and the development of polymeric chains. As the gel gradually dehydrates, the rigidity of the polymer increases, leading to reduced deformability and the formation of a stronger film. This moisture loss contributes to the higher compressive strength exhibited by the treated soil samples.

Overall, these results highlight the superiority of carrageenan in enhancing the strength of fine-grained soils, emphasizing its potential as a biopolymer for soil improvement in such soil types.

3.1.3. Particle size effect

The UCS test results for different sand-kaolinite combinations treated by 0.5% of carrageenan and xanthan and cured for 14 days are shown in Fig. 5. In sand-kaolinite mixtures, the sand extent varies by the amount of 0, 25, 50, 75, 100%. All samples indicated moisture content less than 1%, hence the moisture influence can be neglected.

In general, carrageenan and xanthan-treated soils exhibited remarkable increases in UCS and modulus of elasticity. However, the cohesionless sand showed zero strength, viable strength values were recorded for biopolymer-treated sand samples, which shows the used biopolymers add cohesion along with rigidity to the sand. As expected

Fig. 5. Effect of soil type on the mechanical behavior of CA- and XA-treated soils. a) Compressive strength, b) Elasticity modulus.

from the compaction test results, the soil combination with 25% kaolinite and 75% sand (K1S3) gave the highest strength for both biopolymer cases. K1S3 achieved the highest dry density among different soil mixtures because the fine particles of kaolinite were placed throughout the sand voids to form a strong soil mass.

Treated soils with carrageenan render a higher strength than it does with xanthan by increasing the kaolinite amount. Kaolinite is known as one of the most ubiquitous clays minerals in the earth's crust containing hydroxyl groups on the surface. Carrageenan creates chemical bonding with charged kaolinite surfaces through hydrogen bonding by carrageenan organic functional groups, ionic interactions by negatively charged sulfate groups, as well as hydrophobic bonding. Although xanthan has already shown an effective performance on clayey soil improvement [55,79,80], the lightweight property of kaolinite along with the thick state of xanthan gel engendered difficulties for preparing consistent xanthan-kaolinite mixtures.

3.1.4. Durability by wet-dry cycle

Three samples of biopolymer-treated and untreated K1S3 were made for wet-dry testing. Each sample was positioned in a plastic tube with a diameter of 55 mm, which allowed the soil particles and biopolymer to move freely. The samples were left to dry in a curing room for 14 days after soaking in water for 24 h. The samples underwent multiple cycles of drying and wetting, with up to five cycles conducted, and were tested after each cycle (cycles 0, 1, 2, 3, and 5). Demonstration of the samples from cycles 1 to 5 can be found in Fig. 6.

The variation of compressive strength and stiffness of untreated soil and BPTS (0.5% biopolymer) following cyclic wetting and drying procedures are presented in Fig. 7. It can be seen that wetting and drying cycles effectively decrease the strength and elasticity modulus of both treated and untreated soils. The reduction rate in UCS values was significant for untreated soil with almost 50% after 3% and 80% after 5 wetting and drying cycles, while the biopolymers retained the strength in a viable level after five cycles of wetting and drying by 19.3% and 8.1% of the strength reduction, respectively, for carrageenan and xanthan. This implies that even though water soaking negatively affects the

Fig. 6. Samples pictures during wet-dry cycles. a) untreated K1S3, b) CA-treated K1S3, and c) XA-treated K1S3.

Fig. 7. Mechanical strength of CA- and XA-treated soil after exposure to wetting and drying cycles. a) Compressive strength, b) Modulus of elasticity.

strength, most of the bonding and interactions are greatly recovered over the subsequent drying. From the stiffness point of view, a small decrease in elasticity modulus of biopolymer-treated samples is observed which is in line with UCS results. This means that carrageenan and xanthan decrease the possibility of strain softening and high ductility of the soil.

The mass loss amount of the samples after each cycle of wetting and drying is shown in Fig. 8. As seen, the wetting procedure degrades the structure of the untreated soil by almost 8% erosion after the fifth cycle, and adding biopolymer decreased the mass loss to less than 1%. This reduction in mass weight and the compressive strength of the treated soil can be attributed to the hydrophilic property of carrageenan and xanthan. Once the biopolymer films are exposed to water, water adsorption from the outer surface is begun by the dried gel. some hydrated gel fibrils (mostly towards the outer surface) tend to gradually detach from the main structure and soil particles to minimize the interaction with the remaining film matrix. Due to moisture loss during the subsequent dehydration cycle, the detached film is able to rejoin to the main structure, but a tiny fraction of the original structure cannot be regained after each break-off and redrying. Consequently, a decrease in the compressive strength is measured. Also, the adverse consequences of this cyclic deterioration include less elasticity modulus of the gel, a higher maximum strain, and diminish in gel density [81]. This implies why a gradual strength decrease happens for both carrageenan- and xanthan-treated soils under wet-dry cycles instead of a sudden failure (similar to lime- and cement-treated soils) at the initial stages of wetting and drying [82,83].

3.2. Triaxial test

A set of consolidated drained (CD) triaxial testing were carried out on

Fig. 8. Variation in sample parameters after exposure to wetting and drying cycles. a) Compressive strength reduction, b) Mass loss.

the untreated and biopolymer-treated samples to investigate how carrageenan and xanthan biopolymers vary the shear strength properties of the soil. According to Lee et al. (2019), in a series of CD triaxial tests, a negligible strengthening effect in the shearing parameters were observed when xanthan was kept hydrated i.e., its hydrogel state. Therefore, also knowing the hydrophilic nature of carrageenan, samples were kept dried during the triaxial tests [62].

The sample preparation was performed in consistent with the UCS samples. Compression was applied with a hydraulic jack assuring that a dry density higher than 95% of MDD is obtained. 0.5% (m_b/m_s) of carrageenan and xanthan were used to treat K4S0 and K1S3. Three different confining pressures were applied (50, 100, and 200 kPa) and kept the same for each set of tests so that the shear strength at failure can be compared for different samples.

Fig. 9 illustrates the variation in deviatoric stresses and corresponded strains for the untreated and carrageenan-treated (0.5%) K1S3 at confining pressures of 50, 100, and 200 kPa.

According to the results, for both treated and untreated samples, the higher the confining pressure, the higher the strength is obtained. For instance, the maximum deviatoric strength increased from 440 kPa to 590 kPa and from 1960 kPa to 2200 kPa when the confining pressure (σ_3) was increased from 50 kPa to 100 kPa for untreated and CA-treated K1S3, respectively. In addition, compared to untreated soil, soil treated with carrageenan showed a striking improvement in the shear strength for all confining pressures (for example, strength for the confining pressure of 200 kPa increased from 830 kPa to 2500 kPa due to carrageenan treatment). Residual strength for CA-treated K1S3 were also well above that of pure K1S3.

Fig. 10 and Table 7 illustrate the Mohr-coulomb failure envelope and

(a)

(b)

Fig. 9. Stress-strain behavior of a) untreated and b) carrageenan-treated K1S3.

the resulting shear strength parameters for the 0.5% of biopolymer-treated and untreated K4S0 and K1S3. According to the results, as expected, C' for K4S0 is higher than that of K1S3 (70 kPa and 60 kPa, respectively) and ϕ' for K1S3 is higher than ϕ' for K4S0 (36.42° and 23.76° , respectively). Also, K1S3 showed more shear strength than K4S0 for all confining pressures.

While the addition of carrageenan to both soils remarkably increased the C' , it had a slight improving effect on ϕ' . For instance, effective shear parameters, C' and ϕ' , for K1S3 were 60 kPa and 36.42° , whereas adding carrageenan increased these parameters to 440 kPa and 38.91° , respectively. Xanthan treatment had approximately the same effect as carrageenan on K1S3, having significantly increased the cohesion and

slightly improving the friction angle. However, in the case of K4S0, xanthan could not have a noticeable improving effect on C' while considerably enhanced ϕ' . As a result, carrageenan gave a better performance in terms of K4S0 treatment with significantly higher shear strength than xanthan.

According to Table 7, biopolymer treatment resulted in an improvement of the shear strength parameters for both types of soils, K4S0 and K1S3. Due to the adhesive nature of these biopolymers and sticking soil particles together improvement in the cohesion of the soil is significant. The sticky and powdery state of kaolinite silt acted as an obstacle to prepare a very homogeneous soil-biopolymer admixture. A higher workability in preparing was observed to reach a uniform mixture of K4S0 samples by using carrageenan compared to xanthan. As a result, higher improvement in cohesion was obtained for CA-treated samples. Also, owing to adhesiveness of the biopolymers, particles frequently group together and appear in the form of conglomerations. The soil conglomerations are capable of enhancing the interlocking of the compacted soil and improving the shear strength [84–86]. Internal friction angle is a measure of soil friction that takes into account both inlating force between soil particles and friction on the surface of the soil particles. Large, medium, and tiny conglomerations are inlaid with one another and closely fitted as a result of compaction, which is why K1S3 exhibits better friction performance (higher ϕ') [87]. Biopolymers enhance the conglomeration effect in both types of soils and improve the shear strength.

3.3. Microstructure and interaction models

Interactions involved in the formation of kaolinite/biopolymers and sand/biopolymers composites are explained in this section. SEM and FTIR are used to characterize the BPTS properties. SEM provides high quality imaging which enables a detailed visualization of the mixture and facilitates a comprehensive understanding of soil-biopolymer composition. On the other hand, FTIR identifies molecular

Table 7
Summary of the results of the CD triaxial test.

Sample ID	Biopolymer Type	Biopolymer Content (%)	C' (kPa)	ϕ' ($^\circ$)
K4S0	-	-	70	23.76
K4S0-CA	CA	0.5	350	24.63
K4S0-XA	Xanthan	0.5	95	33.20
K1S3	-	-	60	36.42
K1S3-CA	CA	0.5	440	38.91
K1S3-XA	Xanthan	0.5	495	36.71

Fig. 10. Failure envelope of treated and untreated K1S3 and K4S0 resulted from triaxial tests.

compositions, a real understanding into chemical interactions, and changes in the soil properties [88,89]. Fig. 11 represents scanning electron microscopy images for untreated and treated samples with xanthan and carrageenan. As it can be seen, biopolymer films filled the pores in the soil mass and also coated the grains to connect adjacent particles through a variety of mechanism. Depending on the soil and biopolymer type, different interactions can be inferred as explained in the following sections.

3.3.1. Kaolinite/k-carrageenan and kaolinite/ xanthan composites

Kaolinite $\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_4$ is a hydrous aluminum phyllosilicate member and is an inexpensive and abundant mineral regarded as the most widespread phase among the other kaolin polymorphs and one of the most ubiquitous clays in the earth's crust. The overall structure of Kaolinite containing siloxane (Si–O–Si) and aluminol (Al–OH) surfaces is depicted in Fig. 12. The interlayer space in kaolinite is sandwiched by abundant strong hydrogen bonds between oxygen atoms of tetrahedral silicate sheets and hydroxyl groups of octahedral aluminum hydroxide sheets. The molecular structure of k-carrageenan is also shown in Fig. 12. Due to the presence of abundant hydroxyl functional groups located at the surface of kaolinite (inner surface –OH) and organic functional groups viz., –OH and –SO₄, in the structure of k-carrageenan, intermolecular hydrogen bonding is a possible and important interaction in kaolinite/k-carrageenan composite formation. In this line, the hydrogen atoms covalently attached to the electronegative atoms, such as oxygen, can establish a kind of electrostatic attraction with another electronegative atom bearing a lone pair of electrons called hydrogen bond acceptor atom (such as oxygen in hydroxyl and sulfate groups). k-carrageenan chains, as guest molecules, are intercalated by forming new hydrogen bonds. The other form of possible interaction between kaolinite and k-carrageenan is the electrostatic attraction between the positively surface-charged kaolinite and the negative charge on the sulfate groups of k-carrageenan. The third possible and common interaction can be related to the hydrophobic bonding between the uncharged basal surface of kaolinite and the carbon chain of the k-carrageenan polymer. Accordingly, the three main interactions involved in the kaolinite/k-carrageenan composite formation are hydrogen bonding, electrostatic attraction, and hydrophobic bonding.

In examining the possible interactions in the formation of a composite of kaolinite and xanthan, one must first consider the role of functional groups in the structure of both. Kaolinite has abundant hydroxyl functional groups (Aluminols, Al–OH) in its structure, which are involved in intramolecular hydrogen bonding in the interlayer space of its layers. On the other hand, xanthan polymer has many carboxyl (–COOH) and hydroxyl groups (–OH) that possess the ability to establish effective hydrogen bonds with electronegative atoms. Accordingly, in the first place, the most plausible interaction between kaolinite and xanthan in the composite structure is the hydrogen bonding interaction as shown in Fig. 12. Another interaction that can be pointed out is the hydrophobic bonding between the carbon chain of xanthan and the uncharged basal surface of kaolinite. Xanthan can bond with aluminol groups by interlinking between kaolinite layers through hydrogen bonding, or by hydrophobic bonding on the outer surface of the kaolinite layers without functional groups.

3.3.2. Sand/k-carrageenan and xanthan composites

The interfacial mechanical interaction of the sand/k-carrageenan polymeric chain is the dominant driving force for the sand/k-carrageenan composite formation as shown in Fig. 13. Furthermore, hydrophobic bonding between the uncharged surface of sand and the carbon chain of k-carrageenan is the other driving force in the composite structure. Although hydrogen bonds can be involved in the formation of sand/k-carrageenan composite, their involvement in the formation of the composites is not as great as the previous two driving forces, mainly because sand does not have enough active and available functional groups (unlike in kaolinite mentioned earlier) to be able to establish

significant hydrogen bonding with polymer functional groups. Consequently, the interfacial mechanical interaction and hydrophobic bonding are two main driving forces in the formation of sand/k-carrageenan composite as shown in Fig. 13.

Two dominant driving forces can be mentioned in the study of possible interactions between sand and xanthan for the formation of a homogeneous composite of them: (1) The interfacial mechanical interaction and (2) hydrophobic bonding. Interfacial mechanical interaction strengthens the composite structure by forming polymer bonds around the sand grains as shown in Fig. 13. There is also a hydrophobic interaction at the interface between the polymer fibers with the nonpolar carbon chain and the sand grains with uncharged surfaces. Due to the presence of hydroxyl functional groups on the surface of some oxide structures in the sand composition (which of course constitute a very small percentage), hydrogen bonding can also be mentioned as one of the possible interactions in the formation of the sand/xanthan composite. However, it should be noted that this interaction has a much smaller share in the driving force of composite formation than the previous two cases, i.e., the interfacial mechanical interaction and hydrophobic bonding.

3.4. FTIR spectra of K1S3-Cr and K1S3-XA

Fig. 14 indicates the FTIR analysis of untreated and treated K1S3 with 1.5% of biopolymers. Untreated soil sample shows the K1S3 characteristic absorption bands: Si–O group (at around 1080, 1030, and 1007 cm^{-1}), Si–O–Al group (at around 795, 700, and 534 cm^{-1}), Al–OH group (at 911), and –OH group (at 3694, 3664, 3648, 3621 cm^{-1}). Furthermore, the existence of four characteristic absorption bands at approximately 3700, 3670, 3650, and 3620 cm^{-1} are attributed to the inner (3700 to 3650 cm^{-1}) and outer (3620 cm^{-1}) hydroxyl (–OH) groups indicating an ordered structure of kaolinite [75,90,91]. Comparing K1S3, both K1S3-Cr and K1S3-XA samples revealed characteristic absorption bands at around 2908 cm^{-1} (C–H asymmetric stretching), 2866 cm^{-1} (C–H symmetric stretching), and 1170 to 930 cm^{-1} (overlapped, C–O stretching). Furthermore, the presence of characteristic absorption bands at 1730 cm^{-1} and around 1260 to 1210 cm^{-1} region (Fig. 14) are assigned to the C=O stretching mode and the S=O of sulfate esters [92], respectively, indicating the existence of xanthan and carrageenan in the composite structure. Also, in the case of composites, the broadening of the absorption band in the region of 3500 to 3200 cm^{-1} is due to an increase in hydrogen bonds caused by the presence of hydroxyl (in both xanthan and carrageenan) and carboxylic (in xanthan) groups in polymers. These observations confirmed the presence of utilized polymers in the texture of composites.

4. Discussion

4.1. Comparison with other biopolymers

In this segment, a comparison is drawn between carrageenan and other marine biopolymers, namely sodium alginate (SA), agar gum (AG), and xanthan gum (XA) with a discussion of various aspects. All the biopolymers undergo identical experimental conditions [75].

Fig. 15 demonstrates the UCS test results for K4S0 and K1S3 soil types treated with different biopolymers at varying concentrations. For K4S0, xanthan gum showed limited improvement, reaching 495 kPa at 0.5%, while carrageenan peaked at 1260 kPa at the same percentage but declined with higher content. Agar gum up to 0.5% improved strength, but no further increase was observed. Sodium alginate, however, demonstrated notable strength enhancement, with 1.5% of sodium alginate achieving 1428 kPa. For K1S3, all biopolymers initially increased strength up to 0.5%, with sodium alginate maintaining improvement up to 1% and peaking at 2678 kPa. Other biopolymers plateaued at 0.5%, indicating the maximized effectiveness at 0.5%.

The UCS test results on diverse soils (Fig. 16) yield insightful

Fig. 11. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images for untreated and treated samples, a) Kaolinite, b) K1S3, c) K4S0-XA, d) K1S3-XA, e) K4S0-CA, f) K1S3-CA, g) KOS4-XA, h) KOS4-CA.

Fig. 12. Interaction of biopolymers with kaolinite soil. (a) Carrageenan, (b) Xanthan.

findings. Initially, untreated K2S2 and K1S3 soils exhibited the highest strengths at 417 kPa and 407 kPa, respectively, while the all-sand type (K0S4) displayed minimal strength. Biopolymer treatment significantly enhanced strength in almost all soil types. For K4S0 and K3S1, carrageenan proved most effective, elevating strength from 317 kPa to 1260 kPa and 357 kPa to 2246 kPa, respectively. Sodium alginate was the most effective biopolymer for K2S2 and K1S3 soil types. Xanthan gum had a substantial impact on sand-based K0S4, resulting in a strength value of 1372 kPa. Overall, carrageenan exhibited the most significant impact on fine-graded soils.

Fig. 17 shows the UCS reduction rate resulted from wet-dry cycles test for treated and untreated K1S3. Untreated K1S3 exhibited the most significant compressive strength reduction, followed by agar and sodium alginate-treated samples. After five cycles, agar-treated soil displayed a reduction rate half that of untreated soil, indicating the protective effect of the biopolymer. Other samples demonstrated considerably less UCS

reduction. Xanthan-treated samples displayed superior durability, experiencing the least reduction rate. Among marine biopolymers, carrageenan-treated soil showed the highest durability, with just under 20% reduction ratio after five cycles.

4.2. Carrageenan potential as a novel agent in soil treatment

According to results compared with various biopolymers, carrageenan, a biopolymer exhibiting unique characteristics, holds significant potential as a novel agent for soil treatment. One notable advantage of carrageenan is its shear-thinning behavior, which facilitates easier mixing and distribution within the soil. This property reduces viscosity under shear forces, enabling improved handling and uniform application of the biopolymer. Moreover, carrageenan has shown promising and competitive results in soil stabilization. By promoting better aggregation and particle bonding, it enhances the soil structure, leading to

Fig. 13. Carrageenan and xanthan interactions with sand.

Fig. 14. FTIR characterization for untreated K1S3, K1S3-CA, and K1S3-XA.

improved stability, reduced erosion, and increased load-bearing capacity [93]. This research's findings supported this, revealing significant increases in compressive strength and modulus of elasticity in soils treated with carrageenan.

Another advantage of carrageenan is its resistance to biodegradation relative to other biopolymers, ensuring its long-term effectiveness and stability in treated soils [94]. This characteristic aligns with the goals of sustainable soil improvement, making carrageenan a reliable choice for long-lasting solutions. Additionally, this study demonstrated that carrageenan exhibited enhanced stability over time, indicating its potential for durable soil treatment applications.

Temperature tolerance is another noteworthy aspect of carrageenan. Its good performance across a wide range of temperature conditions enables reliable soil treatment even in environments with significant temperature variations [95]. This versatility expands the possibilities for implementing carrageenan in various geotechnical projects. Furthermore, the availability of diverse carrageenan types, such as kappa, iota, and lambda, provides flexibility in selecting the most suitable variant for specific soil conditions and desired outcomes [96]. This customization enhances the effectiveness and optimization of carrageenan in soil treatment applications.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 15. Comparison of biopolymer content effect on treated a) K450 and b) K1S3 with different biopolymers.

Overall, the current research outcome, combined with the advantages highlighted above, underscore the potential of carrageenan as a novel and effective agent in soil treatment. The unique characteristics of carrageenan, including shear-thinning behavior, soil stabilization

Fig. 16. UCS for different treated and untreated soil combinations.

Fig. 17. UCS reduction rate resulted from wet-dry cycles test.

properties, resistance to biodegradation, temperature tolerance, and the availability of diverse types, position it as a promising option for enhancing soil mechanical properties and addressing geotechnical challenges.

5. Conclusions

In this study, carrageenan was explored as a novel and sustainable polymer for soil enhancement. A comprehensive set of macro- and micro-scale experiments aimed to understand the role of carrageenan in treating soil. The study systematically optimized key parameters, including biopolymer content, curing time, soil type, and durability, through a series of experiments, including CD triaxial tests. Comparative effectiveness assessments were conducted with xanthan-treated soil, employing the same experimental plan. The investigation delved into the interactions between different soils and biopolymers, employing FTIR analysis and SEM images to enhance the understanding of these complex relationships. This exploration of carrageenan's potential offers a valuable contribution to sustainable soil improvement practices, broadening the scope of environmentally friendly alternatives for geotechnical engineering applications. The following conclusions can be provided:

- The addition of carrageenan and xanthan led to an increment in compressive strength regardless of the biopolymer content. Carrageenan-treated soil reached the maximum strength by 0.5% of carrageenan while the UCS kept increasing for xanthan-treated soil by an increase in the biopolymer proportion. Carrageenan demonstrated a more effective performance than xanthan in the enhancement of K450 whereas xanthan performed better in the case of K153 improvement. The more enhancing influence of carrageenan in K450 could ascribed to its better workability, which made the mixing easier.

- The dehydration time for biopolymer treated samples were investigated after 0, 1, 3, 7, 14, and 28 days. The results show that samples gained more than 95% of their strength within the initial 14 days of curing. A negligible growth in the UCS value was observed in the first hour of improvement. The lower the moisture content, the higher the strength is for all the treated samples.
- From kaolinite to sand, various combinations (0, 25, 50, 75, 100% of kaolinite) were made to study the soil type influence. Carrageenan caused a larger enhancement in UCS than xanthan by the increase in the kaolinite amount. However, xanthan treated K1S3 rendered a better performance.
- Durability of the samples was studied through 5 cycles of wetting and drying. At the end of fifth cycle, a remarkable decrease was observed for untreated K1S3 with 80% strength reduction, while carrageenan and xanthan mitigated the strength loss by 19.3% and 8.1%, respectively. The same positive effect in the soil mass loss was observed from 8% for untreated soil to less than 1% for biopolymer treated samples.
- The results of the triaxial tests showed that the addition of carrageenan and xanthan lead to the increase in shear strength, both cohesion and friction angle, regardless of the confining pressure.
- The conducted microstructural study on the effectiveness of carrageenan and xanthan showed that biopolymer films were placed inside the soil pores and formed a polymeric film to bind soil particles via three main interactions for kaolinite soil as hydrogen bonding, electrostatic interaction, and hydrophobic bonding. Two dominant resistant forces for the treated coarse-grained soil can be mentioned as interfacial mechanical interaction by forming polymer bonds around sand particles and hydrophobic bonding. The FTIR analysis was confirmed the presence of carrageenan and xanthan films in the composite structure.

Further work is essential to achieve a practical application of carrageenan in real-world projects. Future research endeavors should prioritize comprehensive studies, including investigations into subgrade improvement, slope stability, and erosion resistance. These studies aim to bridge existing gaps in the field. Additionally, the incorporation of a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is recommended to gain insights into the environmental footprint associated with adding carrageenan to the soil.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Fatehi Hadi: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Chang Ilhan:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Yu Jimmy:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Ong Dominic E.L.:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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